

Commentary

Large-Bore Catheters as Vascular Access are important, but need many Improvements

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Abstract

The introduction of large-bore catheters with the Seldinger technique into the vena cava superior via the internal jugular vein is superior to the puncturing technique of the subclavian or femoral veins. Complications and adverse effects were seen by the puncturing of the internal jugular vein, such as bleeding, faulty punctures, hemo-thorax, thrombosis, faults in catheter material, and infections. Thrombosis, infections, and stenosis are among the most frequent side effects associated with the handling of the catheters by attending staff and with blood-contacting catheters. Besides surface treatment processes, such as ion implantation, ion beam-assisted deposition, and microdomain structures, other new catheter technologies and catheter materials are necessary to mitigate the mentioned complications and the high costs of the catheter-related infections.

Keywords: Bacteremia; Biocompatibility; Biofilm; Catheter-related Large-bore catheter; Vena cava superior

Introduction

Every year, billions of central venous catheters are inserted for intravenous and/or extracorporeal detoxification therapies worldwide. Blood access for acute hemodialysis (HD) and/or acute therapeutic apheresis (TA) is necessary. In acute therapy situations or for a special treatment time, a large-bore or double-lumen catheter can be inserted

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by percutaneous puncture of the internal jugular or subclavian veins, in addition to venipuncture of peripheral or cubital veins [1].

Catheter-related bacteria (CRB) are a major cause of morbidity in central venous catheters, and the source of CRB is usually a bacterial biofilm consisting of a polysaccharide matrix that forms on the inner or outer surface of the catheter [2,3]. Staphylococcus aureus is, in most cases, the origin of the biofilm and cannot be destroyed or eliminated by systemic antibiotic therapy, because the antibiotic drug cannot penetrate the slime of the biofilm. Rough catheter surfaces are an ideal situation for protein deposits and therefore the colonization of bacteria, with producing and forms a slime layer. The bacteria under the slime layer use the organic substances of their catheter material for their metabolism and growth. However, the bacterial toxins can penetrate the slime layer into the patient's blood, provoking a catheter infection. A biofilm is a microbial-derived sessile community characterized by cells that are irreversibly attached to a substratum or interface to each other, embedded in a matrix, and extracellular polymeric substances that have been produced [3]. The biofilm can also be the origin of fibrin sheath formation, leading to catheter dysfunction.

If CRB is observed, the catheter must be removed immediately or exchanged over a guide-wire with a new catheter and additional systemic antibacterial therapy. Central venous catheters are associated more with CRBs than with peripheral venous catheters or arterio-venous fistula [1,4]. Continued nursing staff and physicians' training and the introduction of never-catheter technologies, and catheter material are very important, and have contributed to reducing the incidence of infections to improve patient outcomes and decrease the costs of CRB and catheter-induced endothelial damage [5].

In 1979, we introduced the cannulation of the superior vena cava over the internal jugular vein (IJV) with a large-bore catheter using the Seldinger technique [6]. The puncture of the IJV can be carried out with sonography. The Scribner-Shunt, which was used as a temporary vascular access for hemodialysis for over two decades, was unnecessary. This technique marked a milestone in the history of central venous catheterization for hemodialysis and became the method of the first choice worldwide for temporary vascular access for acute hemodialysis and other acute extracorporeal therapies. The main reasons for this trend were both a lower incidence of puncture-related complications compared to the subclavian or femoral vein.

Contraindications for internal jugular vein catheterization are low, such as inflammation at the point of puncture and unidentified anatomical conditions, e.g., an extended stream or tumors in the neck area.

Besides CRB, another great problem is the biocompatibility of the synthetic material of the catheters and their interaction with synthetic surfaces, which leads to coagulation and activation of the complement system, and to the adsorption of various proteins and the formation of a layer of proteins on the synthetic surface [7]. Thrombocytes, bacteria, and other cells adhere to the layer of proteins, and a thrombus may form, which can lead to blood flow disturbances and catheter dysfunction [3].

Surface properties influence the biomaterial's interaction with proteins, and thus modifying the surface properties can reduce unwanted protein-surface interactions that are implicated in immune responses or improper cell behavior [8]. This result in protein adsorption and platelet adhesion as well as the recruitment and activation of macrophages and leukocytes, leading to thrombosis, and the platelets and leukocytes release cytokines and growth factors, triggering the activation of smooth muscle cells [9]. There is a great need to improve the function and safety of all types of medical implants by developing materials that elicit the desired tissue responses.

In recent years, new developments to influence the biomaterial's interaction and the CRB are available, such as new catheter materials, coating of the material surface with antibiotic-heparin, or silver and/or silicone, cuffs on the outer surface, catheter for tunneling, and installation of an antibiotic-anticoagulant lock into the catheter [2]. One of the developments is the surface-engineered biomaterials for catheters, which can reduce infection rates, thrombogenicity, and other catheter-related complications without adversely affecting the basic design function of catheters. These are the conventional coating processes, such as deposition and spraying, vacuum-deposition techniques, and surface modification approaches, such as diffusion (e.g., nitriding, carburizing), laser and plasma processes, chemical plating, grafting or bombing, and bombardment with energetic particles, as in plasma immersion or ion implantation [7]. The technique based on ionized-particle bombardment has been particularly successful in biomaterial surface modification, primarily because it combines versatility and low-temperature processing with superior control, reliability, and reproducibility.

Modifications of Catheters

A few years ago, the ion-beam-assisted deposition was developed as an ion-beam-based technology for the treatment of catheters from the Spire Corporation, Bedford, MA, USA [1]. This process is typically performed at low temperature under high vacuum. The films with the affected layer deposited by the ion-beam-assisted deposition (IBAD) on all surfaces [10]. One solution lies in direct treatment of the surface with a long-lasting, safe, and effective antimicrobial agent such as silver [11].

The insertion of silver-coated outer-surface catheters showed a reduction in infection rates, but not significantly [1]. The untreated catheters showed a higher positive culture for bacteria of 55 % versus 52 % to the surface-treated ones after removal, but without significance. The main origin is that only the outer surface of the catheters was coated in the order of one μm or less. Therefore, vacuum-compatible catheter materials may be treated without adversely affecting bulk mechanical properties. The IBAD is a line-of-directly; however, parts with complicated geometries may be manipulated for uniform coverage, treated with the above-mentioned technique, and not the inner surface. The untreated inner surface is an ideal part for colonization by bacteria and blood compartments. The study has also shown that minimal amounts of the silver coating leach into the bloodstream [1]. Therefore, IBAD silver-coated catheters are no longer available.

Further development is the microdomain-structured surfaces, which are considered the most biocompatible because they mimic the structure of natural biological surfaces (PUR-SMA, Gambro Germany) [3]. Microdomain structures are used to meet multiple requirements for improved catheter surfaces, including reproducing thrombogenicity and improving antimicrobial properties. The PUR-SMA

modifies the polyurethane coating, which consists of hydrophobic and hydrophilic microdomains with dimensions below 50 nm. The molecules are present up to 50 % and create microdomain-structured surfaces, and if the domains are below a critical dimension of approximately 100 nm, theoretical considerations indicate that interaction with proteins, blood cells, or even bacteria will be unstable and therefore not occur as frequently as soon as non-microdomain-structured surfaces [10].

An advantage of the PUR-SMA surface treatment is the coating of both the inner and the outer surfaces of the catheters, which prevents contact of the blood compartments with barium sulphate, possibly leading to leaching as particles or dissolved in the surrounding media [3]. First results with PUR-SMA-coated catheters showed good biocompatibility, with no hematic debris deposits, low thrombogenicity and coagulation activity, and very low bacterial growth [2]. Large-bore catheters are used for vascular access in 65% of incident HD patients and in 25% of prevalent HD patients [3]. The first choice of vascular access is the vena cava superior over the internal jugular vein. However, larger studies with PUR-SMA large-bore catheters are needed to demonstrate greater effectiveness than IBAD silver-coated catheters.

Infections are one of the most common complications of a central venous catheter, with the source of a bacterial biofilm on both surfaces of the catheter [12]. Another origin of the CRB is the handling of the staff during the extracorporeal treatments [13]. The biofilms are organized aggregates of microorganisms living in an extracellular polymeric matrix that produce and irreversibly attached of fetish or living surface, which cannot be removed unless rinsed quickly, and consist mostly of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which cannot be destroyed or eliminated by systemic antibiotic therapy. On rough surfaces, the bacteria could colonize, produce, and become covered with a slim layer, which is resistant to any antibiotic therapy. The bacteria under the slim layer produce toxins, which penetrate the slim layer and provoke a catheter infection [10]. Biofilm is a microbial-derived sessile community characterized by cells that irreversibly attached to a substratum or interface to each other, embedded in a matrix of bacteria and extracellular polymeric substances that have been produced. In a biofilm, the bacterial colonies generally consist of many types of micro-communities, which coordinate with one another in multiple aspects, and play a crucial role in the exchange of substrate, distribution of important metabolic products, and excretion of metabolic products [14]. Such a biofilm can be the origin of a sheath formation, which leads to catheter dysfunction due to blood reduction and to blood disturbances. The interaction of blood with synthetic surfaces causes coagulation and activation of the complement system and can lead to the adsorption of different proteins, thrombocytes, other cells, and bacteria, and may form thrombi in the catheter, causing flow disturbances and catheter dysfunction [3]. Infections are of particular concern because they can appear at any time, even years after implantation, and are not material-dependent. The infections are usually attributed to microbial colonization of the skin or handling of the catheters by the attending staff. Complication rates due to venous catheter-related infections are reported from 34 to 40 % [2].

New catheter materials and surface modification processes are important to reduce the high infection rates, thrombogenicity, and other catheter-related complications. The IBAD technology must be for both surfaces of the catheter and not only the outer surface. The catheter coated with PUR-SMA on both surfaces, the outer and inner

surfaces, has shown good results [3]. This is a good way to reduce catheter-related complications.

Antibiotics on the catheter surfaces or administration to patients, or disinfection substances can develop resistance by mutation or other mechanisms. The consequences are new materials and new surgical techniques. However, it appears impossible to create a surface with an absolute “zero” adherence due to thermal-dynamical reasons and due to the fact that a modified material surface is in vitro rapidly covered by plasma and connective tissue proteins [3]. It was shown that tunneled catheters have a lower rate of catheter-related infections than non-tunneled catheters [15,16].

Another important point is that Methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) and Vancomycin-intermediate *Staphylococcus aureus* (VISA) organisms have increased in prevalence [17]. The thickening of the bacterial cell wall following Vancomycin exposure is one of the proposed mechanisms of Vancomycin resistance [18]. Vancomycin’s activity may be decreased due to the thickness of the bacterial cell; the result is MRSA and VISA [19]. Antibiotic lock solutions can induce antimicrobial resistance in long-term hemodialysis patients and are therefore not the solution for CRB [20].

The impregnation of device surfaces with antibiotics, antimicrobial substances, metals, and/or nanoparticles could be a preventive approach to implant infections [21,22]. Learning the process leading to the development of CRB can offer effective and therapeutic possibilities [23]. New polymer-antibiotic systems that inhibit bacterial biofilm formation and reduce neutrophil activation after surface contact with different biomaterials are necessary to reduce the risk of biomaterial-mediated inflammatory reactions [24-26]. Other developments are new biofilms to serve as a communication system, termed quorum sensing, or a molecule that inhibits quorum-sensing signal generation among organisms, which could block microbial biofilm formation [27,28]. New catheters with chlorhexidine and taurolidine locks, or polyhexanide betaine, showed better CRB outcomes [29,30]. Graphene-based biomaterials are of interest in combating infections with light. Their photothermal and photodynamic properties boost their own antimicrobial action, allowing them to kill bacteria without contributing to bacterial resistance [31]. Other biomaterials include synthetic polymers such as polylactic acid (PLA), which is a compostable and renewable polyester [8]. Biomaterials such as PLA have been used in tissue engineering, including bone, cartilage, and vascular tissue.

All the new engineering techniques and biomaterials, such as micro/nano surface patterning and conjugation of antimicrobial peptides, enzymes, metal cations, and hydrophilic polymers on the surface, have been suggested recently [32]. In conclusion, all new catheter technologies and biomaterials are not enough to solve all problems with CRB. We need more large improvements for large-bore catheters to decrease the tremendous discomfort of patients and the very high costs of CRB complications [3]. The use of “contamination-resistant” devices helps healthcare professionals in reducing high sepsis costs [33].

A very important problem is reducing the infection rate associated with catheter handling by attending staff [3]. There are numerous available guidelines to reduce the tremendously high costs of treating the CRB, discomfort, and mortality and morbidity of patients. The incidence of CVC-related infections is clearly associated with nursing staff experience and adherence to catheter-handling protocols [34]. A

specific training program and protocolized handling procedure should be defined and adapted to their results. The use of sterile materials and additives protects and resorts to an auxiliary caregiver to facilitate connection to the machine while preventing contamination is necessary [35]. This is very important because the costs of CRB complications due to the catheter material and the handling by the staff are very high.

Conclusion

The billions of central venous catheters, which are inserted every year worldwide for intravenous and/or extracorporeal detoxification methods, are the major cause of the sources of CRB and of discomfort, morbidity, and morbidity of patients. The CRBs are the most common source of tremendously high costs in treating these complications. The staff who are involved in the handling of these catheters are associated with the CRB. Therefore, specific training programs and protocolized handling procedures are necessary to reduce the complication rates with CVC. The use of sterile materials and protective barriers requires a caregiver to facilitate connection to the machine while preventing contaminations are necessary. Many guidelines are available to prevent and reduce CRB, and this has helped bring down the rate of infections significantly, and the tremendously high costs of the CRB-related complications, and help improve the patients’ outcome. New catheter materials and technologies with an absolute “zero” appear impossible due to thermal-dynamical reasons and because the modified material surface is in vitro rapidly covered by plasma and connective proteins. All who are involved in this part of medicine must try all the time to come nearer and nearer the absolute “zero.”

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